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Bike sharing systems: The impact of precise trip demand forecasting on operational efficiency in different city structures

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ABSTRACT

Increasing environmental concerns drive interest in sustainable solutions across various fields. Vehicle sharing systems such as one-way station-based bike sharing systems (BSSs) offer one such solution in transportation, although they pose operational challenges like vehicle imbalance. While many studies focus on optimizing rebalancing operations using trip demand forecasting, the added value of precise trip demand forecasting remains unexplored. This study assesses the added value of collecting detailed trip demand data and developing trip demand forecasting models. To achieve this, we create a simulation–optimization framework representing a city BSS in operation during the day. We use a discrete-event simulator representing the system dynamics and an enhanced mathematical model optimizing the rebalancing operations. We employ clustering in the optimization module to manage larger case studies, dividing the problem into smaller sub-problems. Our computational experiments compare two main scenarios, perfect demand forecast and unknown future demand, as well as several intermediate scenarios where partial future trip demand information is available. These scenarios allow us to determine the trade-off between lost trip demand and rebalancing operations costs, assess demand forecasting benefits, and identify the budget's upper limit for precise trip demand forecasting. Subsequently, we conduct experiments on one synthetic (35 stations) and four real-life case studies, ranging from small systems (21 and 298 stations) to large systems (681 and 1361 stations). Results reveal that precise trip demand forecasting has varying impacts on small and large BSSs, with larger BSSs benefiting the most without significantly increasing the rebalancing operations costs. We also observe that the most significant improvements occur between 0% and 40% trip demand knowledge while beyond 60%, the increase in returns diminishes. The findings of this study offer valuable insights for operators in enhancing service levels and optimizing resource allocation.

1. Introduction

Due to the increasing environmental concerns, various sectors started to seek more eco-friendly alternatives. In 2019, the transportation sector alone contributed 23% to global greenhouse gas emissions (GHG; Jaramillo et al., 2022). Notably, when the end-use sectors are also considered, transportation was the second-largest contributor to the GHG in the United States by 28.5% in 2022 (EPA, 2024). Given the high share of transportation among the emission contributors, more sustainable solutions have emerged in recent years. These solutions include shared mobility, such as ride-hailing, ride-sharing, and vehicle

sharing. The conflicting objectives, i.e., user convenience and the operator's profitability, have attracted the research community's attention, and the focus on sharing systems has increased substantially.

Among several types of vehicles involved in sharing systems, bike sharing systems (BSSs) are one type of shared mobility studied under shared micro-mobility (Shaheen et al., 2020). They provide an economically cost-effective and healthy mode of transportation (Bielniński et al., 2021). It is usually assumed that the shared micro-mobility, such as e-scooters and e-bikes, is a climate-friendly solution to city transport. On the other hand, a closer look into the modes they replace and user behavior shows that shared micro-mobility emits more CO₂ than

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private micro-mobility in Zurich, Switzerland, primarily due to vehicle manufacturing and wrong decisions made at the operational level (Reck et al., 2022). Due to the financial and operational failures, these systems shut down, revealing the importance of operational efficiency in BSSs (Nikitas, 2019).

Ataç et al. (2021b) examine vehicle sharing systems (VSSs) and determine their challenges regarding decision level, i.e., strategic, tactical, and operational; actors, i.e., supply and demand; and layers, i.e., data, models, and actions. According to their analysis, supply-side operational level challenges include vehicle rebalancing operations optimization (Dell'Amico et al., 2014; Schuijbroek et al., 2017) and maintenance routing (Yuan et al., 2019). The challenges on the demand side are short-term trip demand forecasting per station or zone, i.e., disaggregate trip demand forecasting (Lin et al., 2018; Ashqar et al., 2019), and dynamic pricing (Chiariotti et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2019).

In the context of BSSs, trip demand forecasting methods use historical trip records, historical weather data, socio-economic characteristics of the users, air quality, etc. The more information is available for forecasting, the more precise the models are. On the other hand, minimizing prediction error does not necessarily minimize the decision error as discussed by Elmachtoub and Grigas (2022). We also know that collecting and analyzing such information is not always trivial and induces substantial costs, including hiring personnel, accessing and storing data, and addressing data protection and privacy concerns. Therefore, knowing the added value of demand forecasting is essential as it allows the decision maker to know the upper limit for the budget allowance of demand forecasting operations.

Although trip demand forecasting and rebalancing operations optimization are widely studied, we observe a lack of investigation into the relationship between them and the added value of precise trip demand forecasting. Here, we regard this value through quantification of the improvement of rebalancing operations and level of service in the presence of trip demand forecast.

This paper contributes to the current state of the art in VSSs by proposing a framework that allows decision-makers to explore the added value of trip demand forecasting. Our focus is on station-based BSSs, specifically addressing static rebalancing operations during periods of low system activity. The objective is to establish a connection between system characteristics and the essential nature of precise trip demand forecasting. To address instances with a large number of stations, we incorporate a clustering module, demonstrating its efficiency through selected real-life case studies. In line with Nikitas (2019), we argue against a "one business model fits all" strategy and emphasize the need for unique city-specific management and optimization approaches for improved BSS operation. Our work goes beyond experimental demonstrations of diverse BSS management requirements in different cities; it also aids decision-makers in evaluating the added value of demand forecasting specific to the city structure of their interest. In addition, this paper presents enhancements to an existing rebalancing model by modifying subtour elimination constraints to reduce computational complexity. Finally, we contribute to the field by creating new datasets for two BSSs derived from online trip data and conducting experiments on one synthetic and two more real-life case studies. It allows us to identify intricate relationships among city characteristics, rebalancing operations, and trip demand forecasting within the context of BSSs.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the literature review on demand forecasting (Section 2.1), rebalancing operations (Section 2.2), and clustering (Section 2.3) in BSSs. Afterward, we talk about the details of the proposed methodological framework in Section 3. The experimental results of several case studies, including synthetic and real-life case studies, are presented in Section 4. Finally, in Section 5, we conclude the paper and suggest possible future research directions.

2. Literature review

This section discusses the state-of-the-art methods for operational-level challenges, analyzed by our proposed framework, i.e., trip demand forecasting, vehicle rebalancing operations, and station clustering. Although the proposed framework is generic and can be applied to any kind of VSS, we experiment with the framework in BSSs and, therefore, limit our literature review to station-based BSSs with static rebalancing. For the literature on other forms of VSSs and their related problems, the reader may refer to Ataç et al. (2021b) and Laporte et al. (2018).

2.1. Data collection and demand forecasting

Data collection is an essential task if one aims for demand forecasting. For this purpose, some studies in the literature use revealed preference (RP) surveys, for example, system-use data (Bardi et al., 2019), stated preference (SP) surveys (Campbell et al., 2016; Wu et al., 2019), and some combine RP and SP (Ye et al., 2020). The RP surveys are utilized when the system is already established, as it requires realized trip demand information. On the other hand, SP surveys are more flexible, as they do not need a well-established system. The works incorporate both the socio-economic characteristics of the users (Scott and Ciuro, 2019) and environmental factors such as weather conditions, temporal variables, and station attributes (Kutela and Teng, 2019; Ashqar et al., 2019; Scott and Ciuro, 2019).

Following the data collection, works utilize different approaches to analyze various factors in BSSs. Mode-choice in BSSs is modeled using a multinomial logit model (Campbell et al., 2016). Regression models are used to understand bike count's behavior (Ashqar et al., 2019) and to estimate daily bike-sharing trips (Kutela and Teng, 2019). Since the traditional linear regression models assume independence between observations, Scott and Ciuro (2019) use the random intercept multilevel model to identify the factors affecting the BSS ridership. The literature also consists of approaches based on Markov-chain structure (Raviv et al., 2013; Schuijbroek et al., 2017) and neural networks (NNs) such as variational Poisson recurrent NNs (Gammelli et al., 2022), to estimate the number of bikes per station in steady state. Some works use a binary logit model and a linear regression model to identify the stations that need rebalancing and the amount of rebalancing, respectively (Faghih-Imani et al., 2017). On the other hand, Gammelli et al. (2022) claim that more precise forecasts do not necessarily translate into better decision-making in the context of station-based BSSs.

Unlike many studies considering the observed data, Negahban (2019) creates realistic trip demand data through extensive simulation and bootstrapping methods. They introduce an optimization problem and a simulation-based method. It helps to determine appropriate distribution(s), approximating the true demand among several simulated ones.

2.2. Rebalancing operations

The BSSs have started to experience vehicle imbalance with the introduction of one-way trips. It is possible to mitigate or even resolve this imbalance, created by the city's structure or other environmental effects, through rebalancing operations. One solution involves static rebalancing, where bikes are rebalanced when the system is not in operation or serves a very low trip demand. This process employs trucks to transfer bikes to and from depot and stations (Raviv et al., 2013; Dell'Amico et al., 2014; Gammelli et al., 2022).

We see in the literature that optimization models are proposed to find the routing for the rebalancing operations in station-based BSSs (Raviv et al., 2013; Dell'Amico et al., 2014; Schuijbroek et al., 2017; Pfrommer et al., 2014; Shu et al., 2013; Erdoğan et al., 2014; Chemla et al., 2013; Cruz et al., 2017; Ho and Szeto, 2017). The proposed formulations include but are not limited to mixed integer linear

programs (MILP; Raviv et al., 2013; Dell'Amico et al., 2014), mixed integer quadratic programs (MIQP; Pfrommer et al., 2014), and mixed integer programs (MIP; Schuijbroek et al., 2017). Some formulations generalize the many-to-many pick-up and delivery problem with a single vehicle and one commodity (Raviv et al., 2013; Chemla et al., 2013).

Various problem definitions exist in the literature. Some allow only one truck to rebalance the bikes (Erdoğan et al., 2014; Chemla et al., 2013) while in some studies multi-vehicle approach is used (Raviv et al., 2013; Dell'Amico et al., 2014; Ho and Szeto, 2017). The objectives might be operator-oriented, i.e., minimizing operational cost or maximizing profit (Dell'Amico et al., 2014; Raviv et al., 2013), user-oriented, i.e., maximizing the level of service (Kaspi et al., 2016), and both operator- and user-oriented (Ghosh et al., 2017; Shu et al., 2013).

As the computational complexity of the developed mathematical models increases exponentially with the number of stations and bikes, exact methods (Raviv et al., 2013; Dell'Amico et al., 2014), heuristics (Schuijbroek et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2016; Erdoğan et al., 2014), and meta-heuristics (Ho and Szeto, 2017) are proposed. Valid inequalities (Raviv et al., 2013; Dell'Amico et al., 2014), dominance rules (Raviv et al., 2013), branch-and-cut algorithm (Dell'Amico et al., 2014; Erdoğan et al., 2014), and Benders decomposition (Erdoğan et al., 2014; Dell'Amico et al., 2014) are some examples that are used to improve computational efficiency in exact methods. Clustering-based heuristics (Schuijbroek et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2016) are used to decompose the problem. With meta-heuristics such as large neighborhood search and local search, the characteristics of the problem are exploited to achieve the optimal solution (Ho and Szeto, 2017; Cruz et al., 2017).

2.3. Clustering

Clustering is used for two general purposes. The first aims to understand the spatio-temporal characteristics of the stations, which include people's travel habits and land use around the stations (i.e., residential, commercial). K-means clustering (Ma et al., 2019; Feng et al., 2017) and hierarchical clustering approaches (Lahoorpoor et al., 2019; Feng et al., 2017) are used in the literature to serve this aim.

The second aims to reduce the complexity of rebalancing operations optimization caused by large-scale problem instances. The rebalancing operations optimization is solved for each cluster. These clusters can be determined by using hierarchical clustering (Lahoorpoor et al., 2019), k-nearest neighbor (Liu et al., 2016), and an MIP model (Schuijbroek et al., 2017). For example, Lahoorpoor et al. (2019) use agglomerative hierarchical clustering to reduce the problem size. Thanks to the similarity matrix based on the number of trips between each station, they are able to identify the correlated stations. It helps them to discover the group of stations that share most trips. The MIP model developed by Schuijbroek et al. (2017) for station clustering uses a maximum spanning star approximation to solve the mathematical model in real time.

To summarize, various methods are used to forecast the trip demand in BSSs in the literature. This forecast aids other BSS operations, such as rebalancing operations and pricing. However, the literature needs a thorough investigation into the added value of constructing a precise demand model in station-based BSSs that conduct static rebalancing operations. For example, Reck et al. (2022) study the environmental impacts of shared and personal micro-mobility. They develop a choice model for eight transport modes, including personal and shared e-scooters and e-bikes. They show that the CO₂ emissions do not necessarily reduce with the usage of shared micro-mobility primarily due to the two main sources of CO₂ emissions of shared micro-mobility, which are operational services, such as rebalancing operations and maintenance, and vehicle manufacturing. Therefore, it is essential to carefully detect the need for at least some operational services to avoid the negative environmental impact of the shared systems. We detect two studies from Shu et al. (2013) and Angelelli et al. (2022) that

work on the added value of rebalancing operations, and Gammelli et al. (2022) compare different demand models in the context of bike sharing; however, they do not incorporate rebalancing operations optimization in their framework. We see that the literature lacks the investigation of the added value of constructing a precise demand model in station-based BSSs conducting static rebalancing operations, to the best of our knowledge. We also do not find works experimenting with several case studies to illustrate their findings. In this paper, we aim to address these research gaps.

3. Methodology

We propose a methodological framework to analyze the added value of trip demand forecasting in VSSs. This framework involves three main modules, i.e., trip demand forecasting, simulation, and optimization, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The added value of the trip demand forecasting module is investigated.

The optimization module further splits into two parts, i.e., clustering and rebalancing, as depicted in Fig. 2. The former is responsible for creating the station clusters, whereas the latter solves the rebalancing operations optimization for each cluster. Station clusters reduce the complexity of rebalancing operations optimization by limiting the associated activities to a smaller number of conveniently selected stations. The trip demand for one day is simulated using a discrete-event simulator in the simulation module. We consider that picked-up bikes are ridden to the drop-off station, as the practice suggests. The station imbalance is calculated for each station using the final configuration of the simulated day and the desired initial configuration for the following day. Then, the station imbalance of each station, along with pre-computed clustering information, is passed to the optimization module that calculates the best routing for the rebalancing operations. The number of lost trip demand and the cost of rebalancing operations are recorded as performance measures and stored in the database. The dashed arrow in Fig. 1 represents the iterative process of the framework.

We consider two extreme scenarios: (i) unknown demand and (ii) known demand. The first assumes that the trip demand information is unavailable to the operator. Therefore, the vehicles are rebalanced to the same initial configuration every day. The second assumes perfect knowledge about the future trip demand. In other words, the operator knows where and when a trip demand will occur. The desired initial configuration of the next day is determined according to this information. The number of vehicle deficiencies or surpluses throughout the day is calculated with the help of perfect information on trip demand. Then, the maximum deficiency is assigned as the initial number of vehicles at the beginning of the day. If the number of vehicles is insufficient to assign the necessary number to each station, we proportionally decrease the number of vehicles at each station. These two extreme scenarios are then relaxed, and intermediate scenarios are explored. Experimental setup details are presented in Section 4.2.

The proposed framework suggests a generic approach to obtain the added value of demand forecasting in VSSs. The following four subsections present the details of the problem description (Section 3.1) and the three main modules for an instantiation of BSSs, i.e., simulation (Section 3.2), rebalancing operations optimization (Section 3.3), and clustering (Section 3.4).

3.1. Problem description

We are interested in a one-way station-based BSS, where the rebalancing is static and operator-based, i.e., conducted with trucks at night. We denote the set of stations by N and by V when the depot is also included. L_k , ζ_k , B_k , A_k for $k \in N$, represent the capacity and altitude of station k and the number of bikes and available parking spots at station k , respectively. The number of available parking spots for station k , i.e., A_k , is then equal to $L_k - B_k$. The capacity information can be adjusted to consider a BSS with uncapacitated stations. The

Fig. 1. Overview of the VSS simulation and rebalancing optimization framework.

Fig. 2. Simulation and optimization modules in detail.

altitude of station k , i.e., ζ_k , is later used in creating scenarios with spatial differences.

We define the set Γ that is a union of three subsets, i.e., Γ^{req} , Γ^{des} , and Γ^V , trip request, destination, and station and depot locations, respectively. The elements of these sets are γ_ω^{req} , γ_ω^{des} , and γ_k^V , which are tuples of latitude and longitude values of the corresponding locations. The distance matrix Δ contains the distances from origin o to destination d with mode n is denoted as δ_{od}^n , where $o, d \in \Gamma$, and $n = \{\text{'walk'}$, 'bike', 'drive'\}. The maximum walking distance a user is willing to walk from origin to pick-up or drop-off to destination is ϕ . We assume that users are rational and deterministic in terms of their station choice. We refer to the vehicle and parking distribution throughout the BSS stations as its configuration. We define the initial configuration as the configuration at the beginning of the day and the final configuration as the configuration at the end of the day.

We define the time horizon as T . The time horizon is divided into $|P|$ time windows, each denoted TW_p , where P is the set of time windows and $p \in P$. The time is not discretized but drawn for each event according to a Poisson distribution. λ_p provides the information on the rate of trip requests for each TW_p , where $p \in P$. This differentiation makes the simulator flexible at the temporal level to

test different behaviors during the day, such as rush hours and specific event times.

A set of trips Ω happens during the day. Each trip demand $\omega \in \Omega$ has both spatial and temporal dimensions, i.e., the request time and locations of the request and destination, τ_ω^{req} , γ_ω^{req} , and γ_ω^{des} , respectively. The trip demand is not aggregated. A trip demand ω is satisfied when there is an available vehicle at the time of pick-up at station i where $\delta_{\omega}^{walk} \leq \phi$ and $\omega \in \Omega$.

The number of people in the system (η) and the number of people using a vehicle (μ) at that time are recorded as indicators. These indicators allow us to extract the number of lost trip demands, which is equal to the number of users who opt out because of the unavailability of bikes or parking spots.

The rebalancing operations take place instantaneously after a day is completed. We assume that m relocation vehicles are available, each with a capacity of Q . The cost of traveling from i to j where $i, j \in V$, is denoted by c_{ij} , which is equal to δ_{ij}^{drive} . The imbalance of a station k , i.e., q_k , is computed as the difference between the number of vehicles left at the end of the simulated day and the desired number at the beginning of the following day. Note that $q_k < 0$ if the station is a demand station, i.e., the number of pick-ups is more than the number

Table 1
Summary of event types in the simulation module of the VSS framework.

Event	Triggered event	Queue
SimStart	REQUEST, SimEnd	-
REQUEST	REQUEST (if $t < T$), PICKUP (if there is an available station within ϕ)	$\eta = \eta + 1$ -
PICKUP	DROPOFF (if there are available vehicles)	$\mu = \mu + 1$
DROPOFF	DROPOFF (if no parking available), COMPLETED	- $\mu = \mu - 1$
COMPLETED		$\eta = \eta - 1$
SimEnd		-

of drop-offs, $q_k > 0$ if it is a supply station, i.e., the number of pick-ups is less than the number of drop-offs, and $q_k = 0$ if it is a self-balancing station, i.e., the number of pick-ups is equal to the number of drop-offs. The rebalancing trucks visit station k if $q_k \neq 0$.

3.2. Simulation

We implement a discrete event simulator that mimics one day of a one-way station-based BSS; that is, T corresponds to 24 h. The simulator takes the initial configuration of the system, i.e., vehicle and parking distributions, B and A , respectively, trips set Ω , the distance matrix Δ , and the willingness to walk value ϕ as inputs. The state variable of the system is time, denoted as t , where $t \in [0, T]$. Both B and A vectors are updated once an event is processed from the event queue. Within $[0, T]$, origin–destination (O-D) pair requests, which are trip requests from a specific origin to a destination, arrive in the system, depending on the λ_p , which is referred to as the O-D pair request rate. After T , the events in the system are served, and no more O-D pair requests are generated. The simulation outputs include the final configuration of the system, the realized trips list, and the number of lost trip demands.

The simulation module consists of six event types: (i) SimStart, (ii) REQUEST, (iii) PICKUP, (iv) DROPOFF, (v) COMPLETED, and (vi) SimEnd. The triggered events are added to the event list, which is kept in chronological order. Table 1 summarizes the event types, the triggered event(s) by each event, and the change in event queue status.

The SimStart event triggers the REQUEST and SimEnd events. A REQUEST event is generated at the beginning of the simulation for each O-D pair request. These REQUEST events form the initial event list in chronological order. In this way, the simulator keeps track of the time. As soon as a REQUEST event is observed in the event list, η is increased by 1, and a PICKUP event is generated if there is a station k with $B_k \geq 1$ within walking distance, ϕ . If $B_k = 0 \forall k \in N$ within ϕ , the user opts out, representing a lost trip demand, and the η is decreased by 1.

When a PICKUP event appears in the event list, a DROPOFF event, which consists of the desired drop-off station information, say d , is generated if $A_d \geq 1$, and μ is increased by 1. Otherwise, the user opts out (lost trip demand) and leaves the system. In this case, we decrease η by 1. We assume that PICKUP and DROPOFF events are instantaneous.

The DROPOFF event triggers either another DROPOFF event or a COMPLETED event. The user chooses a drop-off station closest to their destination location. However, in some cases, the user might not be able to find an available parking spot at the chosen location. Then, another DROPOFF event is triggered, and the user tries the next closest station. If $A_d \geq 1$ at the corresponding drop-off station d , then a COMPLETED event is generated, and μ is decreased by 1. The COMPLETED event is removed from the queue as soon as the user reaches the destination point, which also makes them leave the system, i.e., η is decreased by 1. The SimEnd event is triggered when the event list is empty.

Although the application of our framework is illustrated on a BSS, the events of the simulator are designed so that the simulator is adaptable to any kind of VSS that is a one-way station-based system.

3.3. Rebalancing operations optimization

As discussed in Section 2.2, the optimization programs are widely used to find the routing for rebalancing operations in BSSs. As this paper considers a one-way station-based BSS that adopts static rebalancing, we decide to use and improve one of the MILP formulations from Dell'Amico et al. (2014). This formulation is selected due to the availability of the simulator and the complete information on O-D pair requests for the following day. Although the authors in Dell'Amico et al. (2014) claim that the formulation (F3) provides better results than (F1) in terms of computational time, we select (F1) due to its convenience to modify the sub-tour elimination constraints. We give the full notation in Table 2 followed by the detailed model.

$$(F1) \min \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{j \in V} c_{ij} x_{ij} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{s.to} \quad \sum_{i \in V} x_{ik} = 1 \quad \forall k \in N \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{i \in V} x_{ki} = 1 \quad \forall k \in N \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V} x_{0j} \leq m \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{k \in N} x_{0k} - \sum_{k \in N} x_{k0} = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{i \in R} \sum_{j \in R} x_{ij} \leq |R| - 1 \quad \forall R \subseteq N, R \neq \emptyset \quad (6)$$

$$\theta_j \geq \max\{0, q_j\} \quad \forall j \in V \quad (7)$$

$$\theta_j \leq \min\{Q, Q + q_j\} \quad \forall j \in V \quad (8)$$

$$\theta_k - \theta_i + M(1 - x_{ik}) \geq q_k \quad \forall i \in V, k \in N \quad (9)$$

$$\theta_k - \theta_j + M(1 - x_{kj}) \geq -q_j \quad \forall k \in N, j \in V \quad (10)$$

$$x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i, j \in V \quad (11)$$

(F1) is based on the Multiple Traveling Salesman Problem (m-TSP), in which m uncapacitated vehicles are located at a central depot. These vehicles have to visit a set of vertices exactly once. This base model is formulated by the objective function (1) and constraints (2)–(6) and (11). The objective function (1) minimizes the routing cost. Constraints (2) and (3) ensure that every node except the depot is served exactly once. The following two sets of constraints, (4) and (5), assure that no more than m vehicles are used, and all used vehicles return to the depot at the end of their route. The constraint set (6) is a typical cut-set constraint used for sub-tour elimination. The last constraint set (11) imposes binary restrictions on decision variables x_{ij} 's. The authors define an additional continuous variable θ_j to formulate the Bike sharing Rebalancing Problem (BRP). This variable represents the load of a vehicle after a visit to node j . q_k is a precomputed vector that is the difference between the target number of bikes for the following day and the number of bikes left the previous day at station k . The additional constraints (7) and (8) define the upper bound on the load of a vehicle. The flow conservation is achieved by (9) and (10).

The existing sub-tour elimination constraints in (F1) lead to an exponential number of constraints. It results in computational complexity

Table 2
Notation for the rebalancing optimization model given by (F1).

Sets and indices	Description
k, l , and $h \in N$	station indices
i and $j \in V$	depot and station indices, where $V = N \cup \{0\}$
Parameter	Description
m	the number of relocation vehicles available
Q	the capacity of each relocation vehicle
c_{ij}	the cost of traveling from i to j
q_k	the station imbalance at station k
\bar{q}	number of stations involved in the optimization problem
M	the big-M value
Decision variable	Description
x_{ij}	1 if arc (i, j) is used by a relocation vehicle, 0 otherwise
θ_j	the load of a vehicle after it leaves node j
Auxiliary decision variables	Description
u_i	the real variables to model Miller-Tucker-Zemlin (MTZ) constraints, which give an ordering to all nodes excluding the depot to prevent the formation of sub-tours

in the order of $\mathcal{O}(2^N)$, making the model intractable for large instances. The classical sub-tour elimination constraints that are used in (F1) correspond to Dantzig-Fulkerson-Johnson (DFJ) formulation (Dantzig et al., 1954). In Miller et al. (1960), the authors introduce a new formulation, i.e., Miller-Tucker-Zemlin (MTZ), using additional decision variables and decreasing the number of constraints to $(N + 1)^2$.

We consider a cost function that is asymmetric in our formulation, which leads to a special case of asymmetric traveling salesman problem (ATSP). The literature includes many works on which sub-tour elimination constraints provide a better solution (Bektaş and Gouveia, 2014; Velednitsky, 2017). Although the DFJ polytope is contained in the MTZ polytope for the ATSP (Velednitsky, 2017), it is essential to consider other factors. A recent work by Bazrafshan et al. (2021) utilizes a multi-criteria decision-making approach, i.e., the simultaneous evaluation of the criteria and alternatives, to analyze five criteria. These are the number of constraints, number of variables, type of variables, time of solving, and differences between the optimum and the relaxed value. Their results show that when DFJ and MTZ formulations are compared, MTZ ranks better than DFJ, especially for problem sizes including more than 20 nodes. Therefore, this work provides an extension to (F1) by utilizing the MTZ constraints, i.e., (18) and (19), in order to reduce computational effort. Constraints (20) are also added to prevent the sub-tours to the same station. For this purpose, a new decision variable, $u_i, \forall i \in V$, is introduced. This way, the computational complexity is reduced to $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$.

Furthermore, we use the valid inequalities proposed as an extension to (F1) by Dell'Amico et al. (2014). Since there is no feasible solution consecutively going through three nodes with a total station imbalance larger than the capacity, these solutions can be excluded. For this purpose, they define the set

$$S(i, j) = \{h \in N, h \neq i, h \neq j : |q_i + q_j + q_h| > Q\} \quad (12)$$

and introduce Eqs. (25) and (26).

In the light of these, we give the modified model as $(F1_M)$. Since the model is solved for the subset of stations that show non-zero station imbalance as in Liu et al. (2016), we introduce another parameter, \bar{q} , that gives the number of stations with non-zero station imbalance. Given these, $(F1_M)$ finds the routing plan for the relocation vehicles. The validity of the model is ensured by the fact that it is based on (Dell'Amico et al., 2014), and the sub-tour elimination constraints are replaced with a set of constraints that are proven to be equivalent to the existing ones.

$$(F1_M) \min \quad \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{j \in V} c_{ij} x_{ij} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{s.to} \quad \sum_{i \in V} x_{ik} = 1 \quad \forall k \in N \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{i \in V} x_{ki} = 1 \quad \forall k \in N \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V} x_{0j} \leq m \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_{k \in N} x_{0j} - \sum_{k \in N} x_{k0} = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$u_k - u_l + |N| * x_{kl} \leq |N| - 1 \quad \forall k, l \in N \quad (18)$$

$$1 \leq u_i \leq |N| - \bar{q} \quad \forall i \in V \quad (19)$$

$$x_{ii} = 0 \quad \forall i \in V \quad (20)$$

$$\theta_j \geq \max\{0, q_j\} \quad \forall j \in V \quad (21)$$

$$\theta_j \leq \min\{Q, Q + q_j\} \quad \forall j \in V \quad (22)$$

$$\theta_k - \theta_i + M(1 - x_{ik}) \geq q_k \quad \forall i \in V, k \in N \quad (23)$$

$$\theta_k - \theta_j + M(1 - x_{kj}) \geq -q_j \quad \forall k \in N, j \in V \quad (24)$$

$$x_{kl} + \sum_{h \in S(k,l)} x_{lh} \leq 1 \quad \forall k, l \in N, h \in S(k, l) \quad (25)$$

$$\sum_{h \in S(k,l)} x_{hk} + x_{kl} \leq 1 \quad \forall k, l \in N, h \in S(k, l) \quad (26)$$

$$\theta_0 = 0 \quad (27)$$

$$x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i, j \in V \quad (28)$$

3.4. Clustering

As discussed in Section 3.3, the rebalancing operations optimization becomes computationally intractable for larger-scale instances. Therefore, we consider clustering in our framework to decompose the problem into smaller subproblems. Ataç et al. (2021a) consider and compare different clustering approaches, i.e., agglomerative hierarchical clustering (AHC) with Ward linkage (Ward, 1963) and proximity of stations as a similarity matrix, AHC with Ward linkage and number of trips between stations as a similarity matrix adapted from Lahoorpoor et al. (2019) and two multi-objective mathematical models developed to serve system needs.

To select the best clustering approach for our methodology, we follow the approach from Ataç et al. (2021a) and use the following performance measures:

- (P1) the total in-cluster Manhattan distance, which shows the compactness of the cluster,
- (P2) the deviation of the total in-cluster station imbalance from zero, which shows whether the clusters are self-sufficient, and
- (P3) the deviation of the number of stations per cluster from the average number of stations per cluster, which shows whether the

Table 3
Rebalancing cost (in kilometers) comparison across clustering methods in Sarajevo and Berlin case studies.

Dataset	# of clusters	(C1)	(C2)	(C ⁴ _{DD})	(C ⁴ _{ICD})
Sarajevo	2	9.728	15.591	12.709	12.627
	10	75.351	372.332	139.880	126.983
Berlin	15	83.393	103.923	163.261	173.630
	20	90.471	120.289	159.271	197.483

number of stations visited by a rebalancing vehicle is balanced among clusters.

We give the rebalancing cost in kilometers for four different clustering methods for Sarajevo and Berlin. Here, (C1) and (C2) correspond to AHC with similarity matrix as proximity matrix and OD-trips matrix, and they favor the performance measures (P1) and (P2), respectively. The mathematical models (C⁴_{DD}) and (C⁴_{ICD}) consider all three performance measures in their objective function where (C⁴_{DD}) prioritizes the deviation of demand between clusters and (C⁴_{ICD}) prioritizes minimizing the in-cluster distance.

The rebalancing costs from applying (C2) increase compared to (C1). The accumulation in a few stations would explain this increase. The resulting solutions of the rebalancing optimization with different clustering methods are given in Table 3. Note that these values represent the total kilometers driven by the trucks, which linearly determines the rebalancing cost. Compared to (C1), both (C⁴_{DD}) and (C⁴_{ICD}) produce more scattered clusters. This fact can explain the increase in kilometers traveled by the trucks. The additional demand-based objective does not work well, i.e., it increases rebalancing costs.

As a result of the preliminary experiments, we select (C1) clustering, i.e., AHC with Ward linkage and proximity of stations as a similarity matrix, for our framework. (C1) clustering performs the best according to the overall criteria, i.e., rebalancing operations cost and computation time.

4. Computational results

This section starts with describing synthetic and real-life case studies (Section 4.1). Then, in Section 4.2, we present the results for the sensitivity analysis of the variants of the synthetic case study and the selected clustering approach for the real-life case studies. Finally, we present the results from the complete framework on four real-life case studies with different city characteristics. As these systems operate with many stations, the clustering module is utilized.

4.1. Data

The synthetic case study is based on the Lausanne-Morges district of PubliBike BSS from Switzerland. As this system does not have too many stations, the rebalancing operations optimization can be solved in real-time. Therefore, clustering is not included in these experiments. The limited number of case variants in the synthetic case study motivates us to experiment with real-life case studies to observe the results of the framework in a realistic environment. Therefore, we present the considered real-life case studies: nextbike Sarajevo, nextbike Berlin, Divvy Chicago, and Citi Bike New York. For both synthetic and real-life case studies, the structure of the trip data is the same as introduced in Section 3.1.

4.1.1. Synthetic case study

We construct an environment that includes the station information from PubliBike BSS in the Lausanne-Morges district from Switzerland, which has a one-way station-based configuration. We assume that static rebalancing is done at the end of every day. This system operates with 35 stations (Fig. 3) and 175 bikes. Since the PubliBike stations do not

have lockers, dropping a bike off at a station is possible regardless of the number of bikes there. Therefore, the capacity of each station is set to infinity. This parameter is later set to a finite number in real-life case studies presented in Section 4.1.2. In the literature, the capacity of the trucks is set to different values between 25 (Liu et al., 2016) and 50 (Chiariotti et al., 2020). We set the capacity of a relocating vehicle, Q , to 40 bikes and the number of such vehicles, m , to 2.

In order to conduct a sensitivity analysis, we create four different use case variants that differ spatially, or temporally, or both. We set the average number of requested trips for the base variant, i.e., the uniform variant, λ_p , for all $p = 1, \dots, P$, to 20 requests per hour. We determine these values following the aggregate values given by the company openly available on their website (PubliBike, 2023). The average number of trip demands per station is calculated to account for the size of the considered network and is used in this paper. Detailed analysis cannot be performed due to the unavailability of disaggregate trip demand data.

For the variants that take temporal differences into account, we set different λ_p values for each time window p . Specifically, we create five time windows: 00:00-05:59, 06:00-08:59, 09:00-15:59, 16:00-19:59, and 20:00-23:59 (Adeyemi et al., 2021). For those time windows; we respectively set $\lambda = \{2, 40, 20, 40, 12\}$. These time windows are designed to represent the rush hours and off-peak. Furthermore, the expected total number of O-D pair requests per day is the same as in the uniform variants.

For the variants which take spatial differences, i.e., the difference in altitude, into account, we again set λ_p , for all $p = 1, \dots, P$, to 20 requests per hour. On the other hand, less trip demand is generated for uphill trips compared to downhill ones. Knowing the altitude of each station, i.e., $alt_i, \forall i \in N$, the trips are deleted from the scenario with a probability that depends on the altitude difference between the pick-up and drop-off stations if the drop-off station is higher than the pick-up station. For the Lausanne-Morges case study, we expect that the spatial differences are significant since the area has a considerably high altitude difference.

The last set of variants, which considers both the spatial and temporal differences, simultaneously uses the properties of both spatial and temporal differences.

Each variant is generated and used for both known and unknown demand scenarios to compare the lost trip demand and rebalancing operations cost. The objective function is built with the cost value being the distance traveled by truck(s) carrying the bikes. Since we are interested in the evaluation of the added value of demand forecasting, the number of lost trip demand and the total number of O-D pair requests are presented along with the rebalancing costs. Lost trip demand corresponds to the number of users who opt out because of the unavailability of bikes.

4.1.2. Real-life case studies

We consider four case studies: nextbike Sarajevo, nextbike Berlin, Divvy Chicago, and Citi Bike New York. These systems operate with 21, 298, 681, and 1361 stations and around 120, 3000, 6000, and 22000 bikes, respectively. The main motivation for choosing these case studies is to evaluate the added value of demand forecasting in different case studies represented by system size, geographical location and characteristics, landscape, economic strength, etc. The data for the first two systems are obtained from their online system using web scraping in real-time and then processed to obtain O-D trip information. Therefore, we present and analyze the data from these two BSSs in this section to show their validity. The data for the last two are publicly available (Divvy, 2022; Bike, 2022); thus, we assume the validity of these two data sets.

The network of the nextbike BSS stations in Sarajevo and Berlin can be seen in Fig. 4 where orange dots show the BSS station locations. In Sarajevo, we see that the network is divided into two main station

Fig. 3. Geographical layout of PubliBike stations in Lausanne-Morges district in Switzerland: station locations (blue pins) and demand generation areas (green areas). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

(a) Sarajevo

(b) Berlin

Fig. 4. nextbike BSS station networks for Sarajevo and Berlin case studies.

clusters. This is due to a small hill between the two subnetworks. On the other hand, in Berlin, we do not see any accumulation of stations in any specific part of the city. It is expected since the city is mostly flat, which makes it easy to access any part of it by bike. In Fig. 5, we see the time series plot of the number of pick-ups (blue straight line) and drop-offs (red dashed line), where each row corresponds to a weekday. Data for the charts presented range from Monday, April 5, 2021 to Sunday, April 11, 2021. The first row shows the plots for Monday, the second for Tuesday, and so on. As conducted in the literature, the trips with unreasonable trip lengths and duration are cleaned from the data sets (Degele et al., 2018).

The unexpected behavior in Sarajevo on Wednesday, April 7, 2021, can be explained by the snowfall that occurred the previous night. In Berlin, we see that the trip demand increases on average on the weekends. Furthermore, the trips are longer on the weekends, whereas

people prefer shorter weekday trips. This can be explained by the fact that people tend to use the BSS more for leisure on the weekend than on weekdays. The same applies to the Sarajevo case study as well.

The presented exploratory analysis of Sarajevo and Berlin data sets does not reveal any significant invalidity in the data. Therefore, we use these data sets in our further experiments.

4.2. Results

We first investigate the effect of knowing the O-D trip requests on lost trip demand in the case of PubliBike BSS in the Lausanne-Morges district. We plot the lost trip demand for each use case variant of the Lausanne-Morges district concerning both the unknown and known demand scenarios to identify the difference (Fig. 6). For all four variants, we see that the lost trip demand for the known case is zero

Fig. 5. Number of pick-ups and drop-offs over a week in Sarajevo and Berlin. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

(with one exception on day 38 for the temporal scenario). Therefore, we see an apparent difference between the two scenarios regarding lost trip demand.

We also compare the effect of each variant on the lost trip demand by simulating 100 days. For the uniform variant (depicted by U in the figure), the average lost trip demand per day corresponds to 5.64, while this value is 7.91, 8.44, and 9.3 for temporal (T), spatial (S), and spatial-temporal (TS) variants, respectively. We also identify these different effects of variants on the lost demand in Fig. 7. Results indicate that the lost trip demand tends to increase in non-uniform variants.

Finally, we analyze whether the rebalancing cost is affected by the trip demand knowledge or variant type. Fig. 8 shows the rebalancing cost for each variant over 100 days. We see that the difference is negligible for uniform and temporal variants. On the other hand, we see that the cost varies for spatial and spatial and temporal variants. This can be explained by the fact that accumulation in specific stations causes deviations from the optimal routes. Furthermore, we see that the known demand scenario causes higher rebalancing costs. The reduced lost trip demand compensates for the additional rebalancing cost in these cases.

Following the synthetic case study results, we first present the clustering results on the four case studies in Fig. 9. Then, the results of the complete framework for all the case studies are presented and

discussed. The utilized clustering method creates geographically convenient clusters as shown in Fig. 9. Although for Berlin, the number of stations per cluster does not differ too much among different clusters, this is not true for the Sarajevo case study. It can be explained by the influence of city structure. The same conclusion can be drawn from the Chicago and New York City case studies. With the obtained clusters, we continue with the analysis of the added value of demand forecasting.

In Fig. 10, we present results for 14 consecutive days, as the data collected for Sarajevo and Berlin case studies include this many days of uninterrupted trip demand information. The horizontal axis shows the days, while the vertical axis shows the ratio of lost and total trip demand, which we refer to as the lost trip demand percentage. As expected, the unknown demand scenario produces more lost trip demand than the known scenario. On the other hand, it is worth noting that the perfect trip demand knowledge does not guarantee that all the trip demands will be satisfied. It can occur due to the fleet size and station capacity, and still might not be able to satisfy the demand. Furthermore, including a user behavioral model would also help to analyze the system better; however, this is out of the scope of this paper. They decide according to the proximity. Thanks to the extended framework, we observe that the benefit of trip demand forecasting in larger instances, i.e., Chicago and New York, is more precise and significant than in smaller ones, i.e., Sarajevo and Berlin. It indicates that smaller systems do not necessarily require precise trip demand

Fig. 6. Comparison of lost trip demand for different forecasting scenarios.

Fig. 7. Lost trip demand over 100 days for the unknown demand scenario in the synthetic case study.

forecasting.

We also investigate some intermediate scenarios: (1) 7-day scenarios, which take the realized demand seven days prior to the corresponding day (previous week) as a forecast, and (2) X-percent scenarios, which assume that we perfectly forecast X% of the trips while the rest of the trips cannot be identified, i.e., we randomly select X% trip demand from the perfect forecast and assume that this will be realized that day without knowing the rest of the trip demands. For the X-percent scenarios, we experiment with four levels of knowledge,

i.e., 20%, 40%, 60%, and 80%, which can be related to reservation-based systems. They can be used to evaluate whether promoting reservations in the system would improve its profitability. Each scenario is run 100 times with different seeds to account for the variability depending on the sample.

Fig. 11 shows the results for 7-day scenarios for the four case studies. The horizontal axis shows the days, whereas the vertical axis shows the lost trip demand percentage. The known and unknown demand scenarios are shown with two different lines in the graphs. The known demand scenarios consider the realized demand a week ago, i.e., 7-day scenarios. Please note that the unavailable data from nextbike Berlin leads to an incomplete graph. We see from the graphs that the difference between unknown and 7-day scenarios cannot be made for small-scale sharing systems. For example, for Sarajevo, the 7-day scenario results in more lost trip demand for days 12 and 26, whereas it is the opposite for days 15 and 17. For Berlin, although we see that the 7-day scenario always results in less lost trip demand, the difference between the two cases is not as dramatic as in Chicago and New York. We see from Fig. 11(c) and Fig. 11(d) that even a straightforward forecasting approach improves the lost trip demand.

Fig. 12, Fig. 13, Fig. 14, and Fig. 15 show the results for X-percent scenarios for Sarajevo, Berlin, Chicago, and New York City, respectively. Each subfigure includes one scenario, and each X-percent scenario is further represented by one line, i.e., the average over 100 iterations, and one shaded area, i.e., the variance over 100 iterations. It should be noted that the scales of the graphs are adjusted specifically for the case study, i.e., the limits of vertical axes do not match amongst the case studies for a better understanding of the corresponding case study. Similar to 7-day scenarios, the small-scale systems, i.e., Sarajevo

Fig. 8. Rebalancing cost across forecasting scenarios for synthetic case study.

Table 4
Reduced lost trip demand percentage of X-percent scenarios for real-life case studies.

Dataset	20-percent	40-percent	60-percent	80-percent
Sarajevo	22%	37%	62%	72%
Berlin	17%	30%	36%	44%
Chicago	33%	54%	71%	82%
New York City	40%	62%	77%	86%

and Berlin, do not exhibit a clear trend in X-percent scenarios. On the other hand, we see a clear improvement in lost trip demand for large-scale systems as the knowledge of trip demand data increases.

Fig. 16 combines each case study to understand the trends better. We note that the vertical axes are the same amongst the case studies for easier comparison, and the shaded areas for the variations are not included. Interestingly, we see fluctuations in the Sarajevo case study for different levels of knowledge, whereas the other three case studies follow a trend. The benefit of trip demand forecasting becomes more visible as the system gets larger.

These results support that small- and large-scale systems react differently to the change in forecasting methods. Small systems do not present a clear trend as the numbers of stations and trips are very small compared to the large systems. The number of trips in large systems stabilizes; hence, the lost trip demand is mitigated with more knowledge involved in the forecasting process.

Furthermore, Table 4 provides a comparison of the relative impact of each scenario within each city. To compute the reduced lost trip demand percentage, we first sum the daily percentages of lost trip

demand for each scenario in a given city, obtaining the cumulative lost trip demand for that scenario. The relative benefit of each scenario (20-, 40-, 60-, and 80-percent) is then calculated by comparing its cumulative reduced lost trip demand (difference between the lost trip demand of the corresponding scenario and unknown demand scenario) to the cumulative lost trip demand of the unknown demand scenario, providing a measure of the reduction in lost trips.

In Sarajevo, knowing 20% of future demand reduces lost trip demands by 22%, and at 40% knowledge, the reduction increases to 37%. These results suggest that early improvements in demand knowledge have a significant impact on system efficiency. However, the slower increase in returns beyond 60% indicates that Sarajevo’s BSS may be constrained by limited infrastructure, such as insufficient bike lanes or station capacities. Berlin exhibits consistent, moderate reductions in lost trip demand, with 17%, 30%, 36%, and 44% reductions at 20%, 40%, 60%, and 80% demand knowledge, respectively. These steady improvements might be due to Berlin’s robust cycling culture and well-developed bike infrastructure. Chicago sees significant gains with early demand knowledge, achieving 33% reduction at 20% and 54% at 40%. The rapid improvements highlight the inefficiencies of the system when the demand is unknown, i.e., the system benefits significantly from better forecasting. Chicago’s gridded urban structure and reliance on redistribution to residential neighborhoods might explain the high sensitivity to demand knowledge. New York City demonstrates a similar pattern to Chicago but with sharper improvements. The substantial gains, particularly with higher demand knowledge, indicate that New York City’s system is highly dynamic and benefits significantly from precise demand forecasting. The slower increase in returns beyond 60%

Fig. 9. Station clusters used for rebalancing optimization for the four real-life case studies.

may be due to systemic bottlenecks, such as station overcrowding in high-demand areas (e.g., Manhattan) and traffic congestion affecting redistribution efficiency.

It is also notable that Berlin is a multi-centered city, with several distributed hubs of activity, allowing the bike-sharing system to naturally rebalance itself more effectively, reducing lost trip demand and enhancing operational efficiency. In contrast, Chicago and New York are large, single-centered cities, where high population density and concentrated activity hubs (e.g., downtown areas) lead to the frequent accumulation of bikes at specific stations, increasing lost trip demand. This suggests that the latter cities derive substantial benefits from partial demand knowledge, and further improvements continue to ameliorate the results, i.e., lost trip demand.

Across all cities, the most significant improvements occur between 0% and 40% demand knowledge, emphasizing the value of even partial future demand forecasting and the importance of investing in predictive algorithms and data collection systems to achieve early wins. However, beyond 60% demand knowledge, slower returns become evident, highlighting the need to tailor BSS strategies to each city’s unique structure and challenges.

Fig. 17 presents the rebalancing operations cost information passed from the optimization module to the database. The horizontal axis

shows the days, and the vertical axis shows the cost of rebalancing operations in meters. Each subfigure includes five scenarios: Unknown, 20-percent, 40-percent, 60-percent, and 80-percent. Each X-percent scenario is further represented with one line, which is the average of 100 iterations.

We summarize our findings in Fig. 18 which compares the percentage changes in lost trip demand (left y-axis) and rebalancing operations cost (right y-axis) across different demand forecasting scenarios, using the “Unknown” scenario as the baseline (0%). The x-axis represents the scenarios (0%, 20%, 40%, 60%, and 80% trip demand knowledge), while the curves and shaded areas correspond to four case studies: Sarajevo, Berlin, Chicago, and New York City. The solid lines depict the average percentage change in lost trip demand, with shaded regions indicating the range (minimum to maximum) for each scenario. The dashed lines represent the average percentage change in rebalancing operations cost, with their shaded regions similarly showing the variability across scenarios. The figure highlights that rebalancing operations costs do not significantly vary between scenarios, as the rebalancing routes tend to remain similar. This finding is critical because it indicates that trip demand forecasting enables better service in large-scale case studies, but not necessarily at a higher cost. Similarly, as small-scale case studies do not significantly benefit from forecasting

Fig. 10. Lost trip demand ratios for the four real-life case studies: Unknown vs known demand scenarios.

Fig. 11. Lost trip demand ratios for the four real-life case studies: Unknown vs 7-day scenarios.

Fig. 12. Lost trip demand ratios for Sarajevo case study: Unknown vs X-percent scenarios.

Fig. 13. Lost trip demand ratios for Berlin case study: Unknown vs X-percent scenarios.

and the rebalancing operations cost stays the same, this supports the conclusion that precise trip demand forecasting is not essential for smaller systems. Although larger-scale systems typically allocate larger budgets for their system operations and are more likely to implement rebalancing operations, this might not be the case for small-scale and local systems. Additionally, the shaded regions suggest that variability decreases as the system size increases, indicating that larger systems benefit from more consistent patterns. In contrast, smaller systems tend to exhibit higher variability due to their limited scale and sensitivity to changes in demand forecasting accuracy. These observations emphasize the importance of system size in determining the predictability and

operational stability of BSSs and provide valuable insights for decision-makers and BSS operators, helping them optimize resource allocation and service levels based on system size and operational needs.

5. Conclusion

This paper assesses the need for precise trip demand forecasting in BSSs. For this, we contribute to the literature by: (i) proposing a generic and flexible VSS simulation–optimization framework to understand the added value of trip demand forecasting in BSS operations, (ii) developing a discrete-event simulator to represent the trip demand of a BSS for

Fig. 14. Lost trip demand ratios for Chicago case study: Unknown vs X-percent scenarios.

Fig. 15. Lost trip demand ratios for New York City case study: Unknown vs X-percent scenarios.

one day, (iii) improving an optimization model from the literature for routing rebalancing operations in BSSs to solve larger-scale instances, (iv) selecting a clustering method to determine groups of stations that can be rebalanced independently, and (v) applying our methodology to synthetic and real-life case studies and presenting practical and valuable insights for the BSS operators. By investigating both the lost trip demand and the cost of rebalancing operations, our framework assists the decision maker by informing them of the upper limit of the budget for demand forecasting tasks such as data collection and development of demand models. Additionally, the proposed framework

allows one to analyze spatial (e.g., city characteristics) and temporal (e.g., seasonal effect) differences.

Numerical experiments are conducted on one synthetic case study and four real-life case studies, ranging from small (21 and 298 stations) to large systems (681 and 1361 stations). Results from extreme scenarios (known and unknown demand) and intermediate scenarios (7-day and X-percent forecasts) demonstrate the impact of spatial differences in synthetic case studies. The findings show that for large-scale systems, demand-based rebalancing significantly improves the level of service without raising costs, while small-scale systems benefit less from

Fig. 16. Cumulative lost trip demand comparison over 100 days for the unknown and X-percent scenarios.

Fig. 17. Rebalancing operations cost for the four real-life case studies.

precise forecasts. Reduced lost trip demand percentages support these conclusions, though a slower increase in returns arises as additional knowledge provides limited utility due to factors like system saturation, infrastructure constraints, operational policies, or external disruptions. This analysis helps operators optimize investment in demand knowledge, i.e., investing just enough to gain meaningful operational benefits without incurring unnecessary costs or inefficiencies.

The proposed framework serves as a base to test various input parameters, such as the number of bikes, stations, and their locations, to evaluate their effects on system performance and support decision-making at tactical and operational levels. Extending the framework to

dynamic rebalancing operations, with real-time information exchange between simulation and optimization modules, could further enhance its utility. Additionally, incorporating simple regression models for demand forecasting and analyzing the influence of system characteristics, such as network size and trip demand, are promising directions. Although a heuristic approach is employed for rebalancing operations, exploring exact methods could be beneficial, especially given the results obtained. Optimization models must be computationally efficient to support real-time decision-making in dynamic rebalancing scenarios. Stochastic programming could be used to account for demand uncertainty, and incorporating a choice model would allow the evaluation

Fig. 18. Comparison of lost trip demand change and rebalancing costs change in percentages (relative to unknown scenario).

of different rebalancing strategies' impacts. These enhancements would broaden the framework's applicability and effectiveness in optimizing BSS operations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Selin Ataç: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nikola Obrenović:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Michel Bierlaire:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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